

MODERN APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Currently, in our country, great attention is being paid to the use of various innovative and pedagogical technologies in teaching English in general schools and educational institutions. This article is devoted to the methodology of teaching English in secondary schools.

Аннотация. В настоящее время в нашей стране большое внимание уделяется использованию различных инновационных и педагогических технологий при преподавании английского языка в общеобразовательных школах и образовательных учреждениях. Данная статья посвящена методике преподавания английского языка в общеобразовательной школе.

Annotatsiya: Hozirda mamlakatimizda umumta'lim maktablarda, ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda turli innovatsion va pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Ushbu maqola umumta'lim maktablarida ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasiga bag'ishlangan.

Keywords: *pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, "boomerang" method, communicative competence, personality-oriented.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогические технологии, интерактивные методы, метод «Бумеранг», коммуникативная компетентность, личностно-ориентированный подход.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *pedagogik texnologiyalar, interfaol metodlar, "Bumerang" metodi, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan.*

Introduction.

One of the most significant aspects of the contemporary worldview is the acceleration of global integration processes, which includes the growth of international cooperation in a variety of professional domains. One of the most significant aspects of the contemporary worldview is the acceleration of global integration processes, which includes the growth of international cooperation in a variety of professional domains. It should be mentioned that the public's need for experts with a respectable level of foreign language competency is continuously growing as a result of these procedures. It is clear that the most efficient method of developing future experts in a particular field's professional foreign language communicative competence is to use the communicative approach to teaching foreign languages to students in non-language departments of higher education institutions, which is generally accepted in many countries. Still, it is important to remember that the aforementioned technique has a number of contentious issues that will be discussed in this paper in addition to its clear benefits. A qualified specialist of the right level and profile who is competitive, competent, and able to work effectively at the level of world standards is the primary goal of professional education in higher education, according to the modernization of education concept. This individual will be prepared for ongoing professional development as well as social and professional mobility. The primary goal of foreign language instruction will be to develop experts who are prepared for intercultural communication in the workplace. Training methodologies and methods need to be updated in this regard.

The aim and objectives of the study. The aim of the article is to analyze and classify modern approaches in teaching a foreign language.

Results and Discussion. The approach to teaching is the basic category in the methodology giving an idea of the language re- searcher/teacher's views. It is the view both on the language itself and on how to master it. It is a component of the language teaching system, acts as the most general lingua didactic basis for mastering the language, and gives an idea of the chosen knowledge strategy, which serves as the basis for the choice of teaching methods and techniques. The approach to teaching is the realization of the leading, dominant idea of learning in practice in the form of a specific strategy and using one or another teaching method. Based on the results of our trial, we can say that our set of workouts was beneficial. When considering each student's unique learning style, the development of linguistic competency in foreign language instruction is successful. Reliance on a personalized method to teaching a foreign language has an impact on the quality of education.

The examination of current foreign language teaching approaches allowed for the explanation of why none of them works for every student and always presupposes certain psychological types of pupils for whom it is inappropriate. The success of the processes of perception, processing, memorization, and use of linguistic information can be attributed to the leading channels of information perception, according to the analysis of trainees' psychological traits that have been identified by different methodologists as crucial for learning success. These traits include different types of memory, motivation, volitional qualities, nervous system features, etc., as well as the full spectrum of cognitive and other styles identified by various researchers. The students' professional knowledge, skills, and abilities formed at the end of the course help to speak and judge about successful learning and the effectiveness of individual work. Relevant and necessary in a multilingual environment: the abilities to analyze and solve situations in the professional sphere outside the box, work with professional literature in foreign, Russian, Kazakh languages, navigate and integrate into a foreign language environment, knowing its nature and characteristics. The results of the study show that the formation of linguistic competency through the individual approach to teaching a foreign language can be achieved by expanding the range of tasks focused on students' psycho-cognitive types. Conclusion. New methods are being developed to implement contemporary societal requirements. Teachers are therefore able to find a unique strategy for each student through the use of personality-oriented, competency-based, communicative, differentiated, integrated, lexical, cognitive, and other teaching approaches. These methods aid in structuring the learning process such that each student receives individual attention while also working with the entire group. Developing students' capacity to learn and solve issues on their own is the ultimate aim of all these methods. As the primary means of structuring the teaching process, a lesson enables the instructor to implement contemporary methods. Each of these approaches requires special preparation, both on the part of the teacher and students. Of course, success depends on many factors — on the teacher's knowledge of the subject and general erudition, in other words, on the teacher's personality. But this is not enough — you also need knowledge of methodological skills, moreover, it is necessary for a teacher of a foreign language. In the conclusion, it should be noted that in practice it is necessary to combine different approaches and use those that are most effective in a particular situation. Based on the abovementioned, we can summarize that each approach is very important in the lesson planning system today; each teacher must adhere to one or another approach, but the approaches cannot be used simultaneously, so you need to have a fine feel for each student before choosing the core of their professional activity. Also, the teacher must take into account that the effectiveness of a particular methodology within the framework of a particular approach to teaching depends on its relevance to the stated problem, the teacher's ability to regulate the time of using this approach, and the quality of the organization of preliminary training, which requires careful study of issues for discussion, development of students' skills and communicative abilities. Modeling common conversational scenarios is a requirement of the communicative approach to foreign language instruction. The word

"revolution" refers to the complete elimination of something outdated and the introduction of something more sophisticated. The so-called "communicative era" undoubtedly contributed to the supremacy. The question is whether it is reasonable to implement the aforementioned strategy uniformly across all nations, disregarding the unique mentalities, cultural norms, and language skills of pupils; in other words, to export this strategy to every nation and replicate it exactly as is. In many nations, pupils are taught foreign languages using a communicative approach. Nowadays, it's common to hear criticism in the international academic community regarding the effectiveness of developing communicative competence in a foreign language.

Scientists from many countries agree that initially the D. Hymes' theory of forming communicative competence was no more than criticism of N. Chomsky's linguistic theory and not the attempt of creating new doctrine in language teaching. In this context it is appropriate to make the following example: it is obvious that not all students feel equally comfortable in group discussions, therefore in order to uncover their creative potential, work in pairs should be used. It is also possible to give students an individual project, the results of which will be then presented and discussed. Due to such variability in selecting tasks all students can actively participate in group work at class. As a result, the effectiveness of mastering educational materials enhances. However, it should be noted that despite the indisputable advantages of communicative approach to foreign language teaching, the representatives of world pedagogical community still do not have a unanimous opinion about the most effective way of learning active vocabulary, which is the basis of the functional application of a foreign language. American teachers suggest using ranks of word frequency. They recommend to practice new vocabulary in real-life communication and to review it from time to time. According to the results of students' knowledge monitoring, English teachers have noted that mastering a foreign language on the basis of communicative approach is much more effective than with the help of traditional teaching methods. In order to develop the skills of fluent speech they widely apply such interactive forms of training as: role plays and business games; interviews; reporting; problem solving; p discussing socially important issues; debates; press conferences; p making multimedia presentations and various projects; communication with native speakers within the scope of video conferences. In view of the fact that achieving communicative goals is the ultimate result of the communicative act, it is reasonable to create the atmosphere of natural language environment in class, because in this case students will acquire the skills of autonomous analyzing language units and understand the sense of language messages. For example, when the teacher sees that students are making speech mistakes, (which are often closely connected with the peculiarities of thinking in native language), he or she plays the role of a foreigner, who either "cannot understand" grammatically incorrect speech, or, in case of an inadequately formulated questions, gives inadequate answers which makes students to use grammatically and stylistically correct speech patterns. The above-mentioned method allows realizing the principle of implicit learning grammar rules that is not by conscious learning language formulae, but in natural way, in the course of communication.

Therefore, learning a foreign language merely at the functional literacy level results in acquiring a primitive "survival language," even though the primary objective of modern language instruction is still developing communicative abilities due to the pragmatic demands of civilization. It is important to stress that using a communicative approach in the classroom does not entail completely changing the subject matter of teaching foreign languages. In this instance, we should solely discuss the use of fresh, more efficient techniques meant to help pupils improve their communicative abilities in foreign languages. Therefore, in spite of the fact that up to now the representatives of world pedagogical community have not fully agreed yet, either it is reasonable to apply or to ignore traditional methods of foreign language teaching in favor of the only communicative approach, we believe that the most effective results of training can be attained provided applying a complex system which should include both the elements of

traditional methods and of innovative approaches in teaching. Within the further research we are planning to study the perspectives of teaching a foreign language with the help of information technologies.

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